

Efficient removal of the pharmaceutical pollutants included in the EU Watch List (Decision 2015/495) by modified magnetite/H₂O₂

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Abstract

The European Union (EU) approved in 2015 a Watch List of pollutants of emerging concern especially harmful for the aquatic environment (Decision 2015/495/EU). In this work, we explore the application of an inexpensive and environmentally-friendly catalytic system based on modified natural magnetite ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-R400}$) and H_2O_2 for the removal of all the pharmaceuticals included in the EU Watch List (hormones: estrone, 17-beta-estradiol and 17-alpha-ethinylestradiol; macrolide antibiotics: azithromycin, clarithromycin and erythromycin; and the non-steroid anti-inflammatory diclofenac). The experiments were carried out with a representative initial concentration of the drugs ($1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) at a circumneutral pH value ($\text{pH}_0 = 5$) within the temperature range of 17 – 50 °C. A low catalyst concentration (0.2 g L^{-1}) was used while the applied amount of H_2O_2 corresponded to the stoichiometric one for the complete mineralization of the drugs ($4 - 6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). Operating under ambient-like conditions, total conversion of the target pollutants as well as the aromatic intermediates was achieved. Notably, total organic carbon was strongly reduced (>50%), being the residual carbonaceous products short-chain organic acids. The applicability of the catalytic system was demonstrated using different real wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluents spiked with the mixture of pharmaceuticals. Apart from the complete removal of pharmaceuticals in relatively short reaction times (60 – 90 min), the disappearance of total coliforms was warranted. Remarkably, the catalyst showed a reasonable stability, with low iron leaching ($<0.7 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and maintaining its magnetic properties almost unchanged.

1. Introduction

The widespread occurrence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in vital aquatic compartments, such as groundwater, soils, surface water and even in drinking water [1-3], represents a growing environmental issue. CECs include a vast array of substances widely used in our daily-life like pharmaceuticals, personal care products, drugs of abuse, pesticides and industrial additives [1]. Conventional wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) cannot warrant the complete removal of these complex substances, leading to their continuous introduction in the environment [4, 5], where they can impose serious toxic and allergenic effects to living organisms [6-8].

Despite the environmental threat, so far CECs are not regulated, although this situation may vary in the near future. In recent times, the European Union (EU) has approved a Watch List of substances (Decision 495/2015/EU), recently reviewed by Decision 840/2018/EU, including several especially harmful CECs, for their monitoring in the EU water basins to evaluate their concentrations in the aquatic environment and thus, to address the associated risks. Among the CECs involved in the Watch List, pharmaceuticals are particularly relevant since they are designed to produce a physiological response in humans and animals. In fact, seven compounds of the Watch List are pharmaceuticals of different types: hormones (estrone (E1), 17-beta-estradiol (E2) and 17-alpha-ethinylestradiol (EE2)), macrolide antibiotics (azithromycin (AZM), clarithromycin (CLM) and erythromycin (ERM)) and a non-steroid anti-inflammatory (diclofenac (DCF)). Hormones have the ability to interact with the endocrine system of the aquatic organisms, giving rise to developmental and reproductive disorders as well as feminizing effects [1, 9]. Macrolide antibiotics are among the most important antibacterial agents used in human and veterinary medicine [1, 10]. They affect negatively the bacteria of the ecosystem and also contribute to the dissemination of antibiotic resistance [1, 11]. On the other hand, DCF is one of the most widely reported pharmaceutical CEC due to its extremely high consumption and demonstrated negative effects on

the environment [12]. As relevant example, prolonged exposure to this drug gave rise to a deterioration in the overall health of rainbow trout, causing renal lesions and gills alteration [13].

In recent years, different methods have been explored for the degradation of CECs from wastewaters. Physico-chemical processes, like adsorption or membrane technology, have demonstrated to be quite effective for such goal [14, 15]. For instance, in Switzerland, where the removal of CECs is mandatory from 2016, WWTPs have been mainly optimized by including powdered activated carbon adsorption processes [16]. Nevertheless, these non-destructive techniques present some drawbacks such as the transfer of the pollutants to another phase (adsorption) or, in the case of membranes-separation technology, the production of a concentrated pollutant stream, requiring an additional treatment [17]. Furthermore, not all CECs can be efficiently removed, depending on their physicochemical properties [4, 18]. In this context, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) appear as one of the most promising alternative for CECs degradation. Apart from the fact that the required equipment is relatively simple, it can be operated under ambient conditions and it is characterized by a very low selectivity of attack [19, 20], allowing to remove most organic pollutants. In particular, the Fenton process is usually identified as the most viable AOP for CECs degradation due to its low cost and environmentally-friendly nature as none of the employed reagents (dissolved iron salts and H_2O_2) pose a threat to the environment [4, 21, 22]. The use of solid catalysts represents an interesting alternative as it avoids in a large extent the sludge generation and the need for pH adjustment. In particular, the application of magnetic iron minerals as catalysts is especially promising. As both Fe (II) and Fe (III) species are present, these materials show a high activity compared to conventional Fe (III)-catalysts [23, 24]. Furthermore, they are highly available, environmentally-friendly, easily recoverable and can be modified to boost their activity [23-25]. Different magnetic minerals such as ilmenite, maghemite, green rusts and magnetite have been applied as catalysts in this process [26], being the latter recognized as the highest active as well as reasonably stable [27, 28]. In a previous contribution [29], we demonstrated that thermal reduction of Fe_3O_4 at 400 °C ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-R400}$) allowed to enhance

the activity of the mineral while maintaining its suitable stability in the catalytic wet peroxide oxidation (CWPO) of the antibiotic sulfamethoxazole.

Although the degradation of CECs by AOPs has been a focus of research during the last years, to the best of our knowledge the degradation of the mixture of pharmaceuticals selected in the EU Watch List has not been addressed so far [1]. DCF has received major attention while hormones have been less investigated and scarce works can be found for macrolide antibiotics degradation [1]. Moreover, most of the works have been devoted to photo-assisted AOPs and ozonation, whose implementation at WWTPs is somehow restricted by the high energy requirements [4, 21, 22, 30]. In this work, we investigate the ability of the affordable catalytic system $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-R400}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ for the removal of the pharmaceutical CECs included in the EU Watch List. The aromatic intermediates generated along the reactions have been also followed in order to ensure their complete elimination in the process. Furthermore, taking into account that WWTP discharges constitute the main contributors to the spread of these harmful pollutants into the aquatic environment, the performance of the process has been also investigated using different real secondary-treated WWTP effluents as reaction matrices.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

The seven pharmaceuticals tested in this work, all of them of analytical grade, were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Their names, molecular weights and structures as well as chemical formulas are collected in Table 1. Hydrogen peroxide solution (30% w/v) in stable form, nitric acid (65%), acetic acid (>99%), methanol (HPLC grade) and formic acid (>98%) were also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Sodium hydroxide (>98%) and acetonitrile (HPLC grade) were obtained from Panreac and Fluka, respectively. The chemicals were directly used, without any further purification. The magnetite mineral was provided by Marphil S.L. (Spain) (ref: 50121500). CWPO experiments were performed in deionized water, unless otherwise indicated (WWTP effluents).

2.2. Catalyst preparation and characterization

The preparation of the catalyst by thermal modification of natural magnetite has been explained in detail elsewhere [27]. Briefly, the mineral was reduced with a diluted H₂ flow (250 mL N min⁻¹ of 25 vol. % H₂ in N₂) for 3 h at 400 °C. A heating ramp of 10 °C min⁻¹ was used. The concentration of iron in the catalyst was determined by total reflection X-ray fluorescence (TXRF) with the TXRF spectrometer 8030c (FEI). The textural properties of the solid were evaluated from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C obtained with a Micromeritics Tristar 3020 apparatus. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to analyze the composition of the materials surface using a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha apparatus (K α X-ray excitation source, 1486.68 eV). The software “XPS-Peak 4.1” was used for peaks deconvolution. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to analyze the crystalline phase in the catalyst using a Siemens model D-5000 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation. A Quantum Design MPMS XL-5 superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) was used to determine the magnetic properties of the catalyst.

2.3. Typical reaction procedure

CWPO runs were performed at ambient pressure in a stirred (750 rpm) glass batch reactor (500 mL). Reactions were carried out with a reaction volume of 450 mL, at initial circumneutral pH value (pH₀ ~ 5, without pH control along the experiment) using the stoichiometric amount of H₂O₂ for the complete mineralization of the pollutants (see Table 1) and a catalyst load of 0.2 g L⁻¹. The effect of the operating temperature was studied in the range of 17 – 50°C. The initial concentration of the drugs was established at 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, which is somehow higher than the representative concentrations of these pollutants in different aquatic compartments [1], to warrant an adequate quantification of the target pollutants and intermediates with the available analytical techniques in

the lab. The performance of the catalytic system to remove the mixture of pharmaceuticals was not only evaluated in deionized water but also in different real secondary-treated WWTP effluents collected in three different WWTPs in the Region of Madrid (Spain).

Preliminary blank experiments under the operating conditions tested in this work were carried out to distinguish the possible contribution of pollutants adsorption onto the catalyst as well as the non-catalytic contribution of H₂O₂ to the reaction. Experiments carried out in the absence of H₂O₂ allowed to confirm that adsorption can be neglected since negligible disappearance of the drugs was observed in all cases (<5%). On the other hand, the control experiment in the absence of catalyst showed its key role in the reaction as drugs removal in presence of H₂O₂ was lower than 5% in all cases. Experiments were performed in triplicate. The standard deviation was below 5%.

2.4. Analytical methods

The reaction was followed by periodically withdrawing samples from the reactor, which were immediately analyzed. Before the analysis, the catalyst was separated taking advantage of its magnetic properties using a magnet. Hormones, DCF and their reaction intermediates were measured by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-UV) (Shimadzu, mod. Prominence-i, LC-2030C LT) using a diode array detector (SPD-M30A). An Eclipse Plus C18 column (5 μm particle size, 4.6 mm diameter, 150 mm length) (Agilent) was employed as stationary phase while a mixture of acetonitrile (ACN) and acetic acid aqueous solution (75 mM) (50:50 (v,v) and a 57:43 (v,v) for hormones and DCF, respectively) was used as mobile phase. The analysis was performed at 270 nm.

Macrolide antibiotics were quantified by high performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (HPLC MS-MS) (HPLC-1200, 6410 TQ Agilent) using an ACE Excel 2μm C18 column (150 mm length, 3 mm diameter) as stationary phase. The analyses were performed using a mixture of water (0.1% formic acid) and methanol in gradient elution (20-100% (v/v) MeOH in 15

min) as mobile phase. All MS data acquisition and processing were carried out using the software package LC/MSD MassHunter. External mass calibration for the positive ESI mode was conducted prior to analysis in the mass range of m/z 180 – 1000.

The analysis of short-chain organic acids was performed by ion chromatography (Metrohm 790 IC) with chemical suppression using a conductivity detector. Total organic carbon (TOC) was determined with a TOC analyzer (Shimadzu TOC V_{SCH}). The concentration of H₂O₂ and dissolved iron in the reaction medium were measured by colorimetric titration with a Shimadzu UV / Vis 1603 spectrophotometer. The titanium oxysulfate [27] and the *o*-phenantroline methods were used [31], respectively.

The removal of total coliforms and *E. coli* was also investigated in the experiments performed in real WWTP effluents. Total coliforms and *E. coli* were determined using the Colilert-18 test (ISO 9308-2:2012). The results are expressed as the most probable number of coliforms (MPN) per 100 mL, being the quantification limit 1 MPN/100 mL.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst characterization

The modified mineral Fe₃O₄-R400 was fully characterized in a previous contribution where the effect of the modification of natural magnetite by reduction and oxidation thermal treatments was investigated [29]. Briefly, the iron content corresponded to the theoretical one for the pure mineral (73% wt.), the specific surface area was around 7 m² g⁻¹, which is also consistent with the exhibited by iron minerals [25, 32], and the particles showed a spherical shape with an average diameter of 0.2 μm (see Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Material for SEM image). The thermal treatment of natural magnetite did not change the crystalline structure of the solid. In this sense, all peaks of the XRD pattern of Fe₃O₄-R400 corresponded to magnetite (Fig. 1a). Nevertheless, it allowed to increase the proportion of Fe(II)/Fe(III) species on the catalyst surface from 0.42 to 0.63,

which was demonstrated to be a key factor for the CWPO activity enhancement showed by this solid [29]. The deconvolution of the XPS profile is depicted in Fig. 1b. In the same line, the magnetic properties of the material were slightly higher than those of pristine magnetite (81.5 vs. 77.8 emu g⁻¹) (Fig. 1c).

3.2. Degradation of hormones

The evolution of the three hormones investigated in this work (E1, E2, EE2) upon CWPO at different temperatures (17 – 50 °C) is depicted in Fig. 2. As observed, the complete removal of all hormones was achieved although different reaction times were necessary depending on the compound and the operating temperature. This reaction parameter showed a marked effect on the kinetics of the process. In this sense, around 2 – 2.5 h, 1 – 1.5 h and less than 0.5 h were required operating at 17, 25 and 50 °C, respectively. These results can be favorably compared to those achieved with other conventional technologies investigated for the removal of hormones such as adsorption or membrane separation. Grover et al. (2011) evaluated the removal of endocrine disrupting chemicals at a full-scale granular activated carbon (GAC) post-tertiary plant in South-West England. In that work, significant but not complete removal of the three hormones was observed (E1>43%, E2>43%, EE2=64%). Higher efficiencies for the separation of these hormones (around 70%) were achieved in the treatment of surface water by nanofiltration [23]. Nevertheless, a multi-barrier approach (integration of nanofiltration with UV photolysis) was proposed to increase the overall hormone removal efficiency and thus, reaching their complete elimination. With regard to the results obtained by other AOPs, ozonation and photo-assisted processes have been the main focus of research [33, 34]. Dimitroula et al. (2012) applied solar photocatalysis using different TiO₂ catalysts for the abatement of EE2. Under optimized operating conditions, up to 1 h was required to achieve the complete removal of EE2 at 25 °C but using considerably high catalyst concentrations (~550 mg L⁻¹). Ozonation also allowed to reduce significantly the concentration of the hormones, reaching conversions above 77% [1, 35]. Moreira et al. (2015) proposed the combined

photocatalytic ozonation treatment as optimum system to achieve the complete degradation of the three hormones.

The degradation of hormones upon CWPO showed two stages. In the first one, corresponding to the first stages of the reaction (<1 min), hormone concentration suffered a sharp decrease (Fig. 2). Afterwards, the evolution of hormones was successfully described by a pseudo-first order kinetic model. This behavior has been also observed in the degradation of hormones upon solar photo-Fenton [34]. The values of the pseudo-first order rate constants as well as apparent activation energy are collected in Table 2. The hormones exhibited similar reactivity towards CWPO and the activation energy values were around 50 kJ mol^{-1} , which is a comparable value to the ones typically reported for pharmaceuticals or pesticides oxidation by Fenton-like processes ($20 - 80 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$)[15, 17, 29, 36-38]. This behavior was expected given the structural similarities of the three molecules (Table 1). It must be noted that also pK_a (10.34, 10.46 and 10.40 for E1, E2 and EE2, respectively) and $\text{Log } K_{ow}$ values (3.4, 3.94 and 4.1 for E1, E2 and EE2, respectively) of the three molecules are comparable [39]. Nevertheless, the oxidation rates of the hormones decreases in the order $EE2 > E1 > E2$, which is also consistent to the results obtained in photo-Fenton [34]. This order of reactivity could be related to the different substituents at the C17 position of the molecule [20]. E2 shows a hydroxyl group while E1 presents a ketone group and EE2 has both an ethynyl and a hydroxyl groups. Although $\text{HO}\cdot$ is highly reactive and unselective, it appears to be weakly electrophilic, being the order in carbon bond reactivity tertiary > secondary > primary [20], explaining the high reactivity of the ethynyl group of EE2. On the other hand, the electron-withdrawing ability of a ketone group is higher than that of an alcohol group, which could demonstrate the higher oxidation rate of E1 compared to E2.

To assess the efficiency of an AOP process, it is crucial to analyze the fate of the aromatic intermediates generated along reaction as they can show even higher toxicity than the target pollutants [4, 40]. This fact represents a major concern in the application of AOP technologies. The evolution of the aromatic intermediates upon CWPO was followed by HPLC-UV and the complete

degradation of them was verified at the end of the reaction. As representative example, the results obtained in the degradation of EE2 at 25 °C are depicted in Fig. 3a. Three major peaks were observed, but these compounds were completely eliminated at the end of the process (90 min) operating at 25 and 50 °C, although some remained when the process was carried out at 17 °C (see Fig. S2 of the Supplementary Material for the evolution of the intermediates at different temperatures). According to the literature [24, 29], those intermediates correspond to hydroxylated species formed either by the addition of a hydroxyl group to the compound at different positions of the aromatic rings and/or by the replacement of some functional group by a hydroxyl one. Notably, all of them were completely removed upon reaction. Consistent with these results, effluent mineralization grades around 50 – 60% were achieved at the end of the process operating at temperatures at or above 25 °C while less than 20% was reached at 17 °C. This demonstrates that temperature did not only affect the kinetics of the process but also the extension of the reaction. Remarkably, the residual organic carbon in the effluent was in the form of non-toxic short chain organic acids such as formic, acetic and oxalic acids (see Table S2 of the Supplementary Material). Accordingly, the pH of the reaction medium was somewhat decreased to values within the range of 3.5 – 4.0. On the other hand, H₂O₂ consumption at the end of the treatment was within the range of 40 – 70% under the temperature range investigated. Regarding catalyst stability, it must be noted that the amount of iron leached was below 0.4 mg L⁻¹ at the end of the reaction, which represents a 0.3% of the initial iron concentration in the solid.

3.3. Degradation of macrolide antibiotics

Among the different classes of pharmaceuticals, the presence of antibiotics in the aquatic environment is of special concern given their potential role in the development of resistant mechanisms by bacteria. The removal of antibiotic macrolides by AOPs has been scarcely investigated in the literature, and so far it has been only focused on photocatalysis and ozonation [41-44] revealing a lack of knowledge regarding the efficiency of other AOPs [1].

The evolution of the three macrolide antibiotics upon CWPO with Fe₃O₄-R400/H₂O₂ at different temperatures is depicted in Fig. 4. Remarkably, and similar to the behavior previously observed in hormones degradation, these compounds showed a high reactivity towards CWPO. Reaction times of 1.5 h, 1 h and only 15 min were required to achieve their complete conversion operating at 17, 25 and 50°C, respectively. In previous works dealing with the degradation of these compounds by AOPs, global parameters such as TOC [41] or microorganism growth inhibition [43] have been followed instead of the antibiotics concentration and thus, comparison of the results is not straightforward. Nevertheless, as representative example, it could be mentioned that up to 1.5 h were required to achieve 90% TOC reduction of ERM upon UV-A photocatalysis using Degussa P25 TiO₂ catalyst (250 mg L⁻¹) [41].

Macrolide antibiotics degradation was successfully described by pseudo-first order reaction. The resulting rate constants and activation energy values are collected in Table 2. In general, quite similar results were obtained for the three compounds, which is consistent with their similar molecular structures (Table 1). Nevertheless, while the difference in the reactivity of CLM and ERM towards CWPO was practically negligible, AZM showed slightly lower oxidation rates under all the operating conditions tested in this work (Table 2). CLM and ERM are 14-member lactone rings structures composed of carbon and oxygen. The only difference between them is the presence of a methoxy or a hydroxyl group at position 6 on the carbon ring. Both substituents have similar electron-withdrawing ability and they do not seem to modify significantly the reactivity of the molecule. On the other hand, AZM is an azalide that contains a 15-membered ring consisting of carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen. AZM shows a methyl-substituted nitrogen instead of a carbonyl group (as CLM and ERM), which improve the stability of the molecule and reduce its reactivity to HO· attack.

The obtained apparent activation energy values were in the range 45-50 kJ mol⁻¹, similar to those values achieved upon the CWPO of other antibiotics under similar operating conditions such

as sulfamethoxazole (49.5 kJ mol^{-1}) and trimethoprim (65.7 kJ mol^{-1}), but lower than that of the highly refractory antibiotic metronidazole (82.9 kJ mol^{-1}) [36].

The evolution of aromatic intermediates could not be followed upon macrolide antibiotics degradation because a high number of molecules were obtained. However, all aromatic intermediates were completely eliminated once the target pollutant was removed under the operating conditions tested in this work, obtaining short-chain organic acids as final oxidation products (see Table S2 of the Supplementary Material), with the associated decrease on the pH value to 3.5 – 4.0. Effluent mineralization yields were around 50 – 60% while H_2O_2 consumption was within the range of 55 to 70% operating at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ or above. At $17 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, TOC mineralization was below 20% and H_2O_2 conversion around 40%. Fe leached to the reaction medium was around 0.5 mg L^{-1} in all cases, which is similar to the dissolved iron concentrations obtained in hormones degradation.

3.4. Degradation of diclofenac

Among the drugs collected in the EU Decision 2015/495, DCF has been by far the most investigated pharmaceutical in the literature [1]. This could be due to the fact that anti-inflammatory drugs are over-the-counter in most countries, which increases the chances for consumption and thus, their presence in the environment with the associated risks. In particular, DCF is often recognized as the “world’s most popular pain killer” [12] and thus, the development of efficient technologies for its removal is crucial.

The evolution of DCF upon CWPO at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 5. As observed, the anti-inflammatory was completely converted in considerably longer reaction times than those required for hormones and macrolide antibiotics (Fig. 2 and Fig. 4). In this sense, 5 h, 2 h and 40 min were required to achieve the complete conversion of the drug at 17 , 25 and 50°C , respectively. These results are in agreement with the reported in previous works focused on the

removal of DCF by CWPO [45, 46]. Hofmann et al. (2007) investigated the CWPO of DCF (20 mg L⁻¹) with industrial metal oxide catalysts at temperatures in the range of 40 – 60 °C. Even using significantly higher concentrations of H₂O₂ (1.65 g L⁻¹) and catalyst (10 g L⁻¹) than those employed in the current work, from 40 min to 2 h were required to achieve the complete removal of the drug depending on the catalyst used. The results obtained in this work can be also favorably compared with those obtained in the degradation of DCF by the conventional homogeneous Fenton process [46] where 74% DCF removal was achieved after 4 h reaction time under optimized conditions ([DCF]₀ = 9 mg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = 35 mg L⁻¹; [Fe²⁺] = 1 mg L⁻¹; pH₀ = 3.5; 27 °C). More recently, Bae et al. (2013) used an iron mineral (pyrite) as catalyst for the CWPO of DCF ([DCF]₀ = 5 mg L⁻¹; [pyrite]₀ = 60 mg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = 34 mg L⁻¹; pH₀ = 4; 25 °C). A quite fast removal of the drug (2 min) was achieved but using a H₂O₂ dose far above the stoichiometric amount and leading to important amounts of dissolved iron (~4 mg L⁻¹ dissolved iron) in the reaction effluent.

Consistent with the results obtained in the degradation of hormones and macrolide antibiotics, the removal of DCF was successfully described by pseudo-first order kinetics. The values of the rate constants and activation energy are collected in Table 2. On the basis of these results, it can be confirmed that DCF is the most stable drug among the pharmaceutical CECs collected in the EU Watch List towards CWPO. Rate constants obtained were up to 5 times lower than those exhibited by hormones and macrolide antibiotics, and the highest activation energy value (76 kJ mol⁻¹) was calculated, close to the highly persistent antibiotic metronidazole [36].

Fig. 3b shows the evolution of the aromatic intermediates detected along the CWPO of DCF at 25 °C. All of them were completely removed after 150 min of reaction (checked by HPLC-UV). However, it is noteworthy that 30 more min were required once DCF was degraded to achieve an effluent free of aromatic intermediates. Operating at 17 °C, the complete removal of the intermediates was not achieved even in 5 h reaction time while complete disappearance was observed at 50 °C in 1 h (see Fig. S3 of the Supplementary Material for intermediates evolution at 17 and 50 °C). CWPO effluents showed mineralization degrees around 50 – 60% with the exception

of the reaction performed at 17 °C where TOC reduction was around 15%, being the final reaction products short-chain organic acids (see Table S2 of the Supplementary Materials). In line with the aforementioned results, the pH of the reaction medium was slightly decreased to 3.5 – 4.0. The consumption of H₂O₂ was above 60% operating at ≥25 °C (see Fig. S4 of the Supplementary Material). In line with the results obtained with the other drugs, dissolved iron concentration in the reaction medium was below 0.5 mg L⁻¹.

3.5. Proof of concept: treatment of the pharmaceuticals mixture in real WWTP effluents

In order to assess the process efficiency for tertiary treatment, a new set of experiments was carried out using different real secondary-treated WWTP effluents spiked with the mixture of pharmaceuticals (1000 µg L⁻¹ of each drug). Due to the higher load of organic matter present in these effluents, the amount of catalyst used in these experiments was 2 g L⁻¹, while the dose of H₂O₂ was established at the stoichiometric one for the mineralization of the mixture of target pollutants (35 mg L⁻¹). The characterization of the raw aqueous matrices is collected in Table 3. The evolution of the drugs along the oxidation process is depicted in Fig. 6. As can be seen, complete degradation of all target pollutants was achieved in relatively short reaction times (60 – 90 min) regardless of the composition of the aqueous matrix tested, confirming the versatility of this catalytic system for the removal of these pollutants. It must be noted that although WWTP3 present a relatively high amount of iron (1.6 mg L⁻¹), it did not affect the kinetics of the process as it is reasonably in the form of Fe hydroxydes given the slightly basic pH of the effluent. On the other hand, the high initial TOC concentration did not affect the performance of the system as well, probably because it corresponds to molecules much less reactive towards CWPO than the pharmaceuticals.

Table 4 shows the pseudo-first order rate constants obtained operating at 25 °C. In general, the reactivity in these multi-component systems followed the same trend as the respective single-

component ones (Table 2). In this sense, DCF showed the slowest oxidation rate whereas the degradation rates for hormones and macrolide antibiotics were quite similar. Nonetheless, the obtained rate constants for DCF removal in mixture, regardless of the WWTP composition, were higher than the one showed in the degradation of the isolated drug. On the other hand, in general, the rate constants obtained for hormones and macrolide antibiotics in the mixture were somehow lower than those obtained when they were independently treated. These results can be explained by the formation of highly reactive species at the initial stages of the CWPO of hormones and antibiotic macrolides, which could promote the oxidation of the most refractory species (DCF) [36].

The consumption of H_2O_2 was quite similar for the different aqueous matrices (65%, 60% and 75% for WWTP1, WWTP2 and WWTP3 effluents, respectively). The slight differences can be attributed to the different composition of the real matrices. For instance, the conductivity, IC and TOC values of WWTP3 were much higher than those exhibited by the other two matrices. It is well-known that bicarbonates, chlorides and sulfates can promote scavenging effects leading to the formation of the respective radicals, whose oxidation potential is much lower than that of hydroxyl [33]. On the other hand, the organic species present in the matrix could also compete with the pollutants for hydroxyl radicals. TOC conversion was around 35% in WWTP1 and WWTP2 effluents and below 20% in WWTP 3 effluent. These results are consistent with the initial TOC content of these aqueous matrices. Whereas the former showed less than 4 mg L^{-1} TOC, the latter showed up to 17.8 mg L^{-1} . It must be noted that the stoichiometric amount of H_2O_2 for the complete mineralization of the drug was used and thus, the mineralization of the effluent could not be possible under these operating conditions. As in the case of individual pharmaceuticals, the final pH obtained for all real matrices was a value close to 3.5. With regard to the iron leached from the catalyst, it is noteworthy to mention that only $\sim 0.7 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ were quantified at the end of the treatment (once the initial amount of dissolved iron in the real effluent was deducted). Furthermore, it should be highlighted that its magnetic properties remained practically unchanged (81, 80 and 78

emu g⁻¹ were measured for the used catalysts in WWTP1, WWTP2 and WWTP3 matrices, respectively).

The system Fe₃O₄-R400/H₂O₂ was not only capable of removing the target pollutants in question but also allowed to eliminate pathogens. WWTPs received antibiotic pollutants from domestic, hospitals and animal production sludge, and thus, they are major sources of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Disinfection of WWTP discharges is important considering both public health and environmental issues as it can reduce the number of bacteria and the risk of pathogen transmission [47]. The content of total coliforms and *E. coli* was determined in the three WWTP effluents after the CWPO treatment. Remarkably, the complete removal of total coliforms and *E. coli* was achieved at the end of the reactions (90 min).

To get further insights about the elimination of the microorganisms upon the treatment, further experiments were carried out with the effluent showing the highest microbial load (WWTP3) to follow its evolution. Blank experiments in the absence of H₂O₂ and catalyst were also performed. The results obtained are depicted in Fig. 7. For comparison purposes, the removal of the most refractory drug (DCF) was also depicted. As observed, the complete inactivation of total coliforms and *E. coli* was achieved in less than 5 min reaction time and thus, this catalytic system warrants the inactivation of pathogens as the removal of drugs is by far much slower. It should be also noted that the only presence of H₂O₂ also allowed to inactivate the bacteria but up to 1 h was required in this case. This can be explained by the well-known disinfection properties of H₂O₂ [48, 49]. On the other hand, the removal of coliforms also occurred with the catalyst in absence of H₂O₂. The complete removal was achieved in 3 h. A number of works have shown that magnetic nanoparticles, iron-based composite materials and also iron hydroxide particles can effectively remove pathogenic bacteria [50-53]. The main mechanism is the adsorption of bacteria due to electrostatic interactions as well as direct bond formation between macromolecules at cell surface and functional groups at catalytic particles surface [51]. In any case, the synergistic effect between

the catalyst and H₂O₂ was clear, requiring less than 5 min to achieve the complete elimination of total coliforms and *E. coli*.

4. Conclusions

The inexpensive catalytic system Fe₃O₄-R400/H₂O₂ has proved to be effective for the removal of the pharmaceuticals included in the EU Watch List (hormones, macrolide antibiotics and anti-inflammatory) operating with a representative initial concentration of drugs ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) under ambient conditions and circumneutral pH (pH₀ ~ 5). Complete elimination of the target pollutants as well as their aromatic intermediates was achieved in relatively short reaction times (60 – 90 min) employing a catalyst concentration in the range of 0.2 – 2.0 g L⁻¹ and the stoichiometric dose of H₂O₂. Remarkably, mineralization yields were above 50%, being the residual oxidation products biodegradable and non-toxic short-chain organic acids. Furthermore, the process was successfully applied to the treatment of the drugs mixture in different real WWTP effluents, where not only the pharmaceutical pollutants were removed but also the microbiological content, achieving the complete elimination of total coliforms. It should be also noted that the catalyst showed a fairly good stability, with low iron leaching and maintaining its magnetic properties unchanged.

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Table and Figure captions

Table 1. Pharmaceuticals tested and theoretical stoichiometry for their mineralization by CWPO.

Table 2. Values of the apparent rate constants and activation energy.

Table 3. Representative analysis of the real WWTP effluents.

Table 4. Values of the apparent rate constants in the CWPO of the mixture of pharmaceuticals in different WWTP effluents at 25 °C.

Fig. 1. Characterization of Fe₃O₄-R400: XRD pattern (major peaks are identified using ICDD PDFs 01-080-6402 (Fe₃O₄)) (a), deconvolution of the Fe 3p core-level spectra (b) and magnetization hysteresis loop (c).

Fig. 2. Time-course of E1, E2 and EE2 (individually treated) upon CWPO with Fe₃O₄-R400 at different temperatures ([Hormone]₀ = 1000 µg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = stoichiometric amount; [Fe₃O₄-R400] = 0.2 g L⁻¹; pH₀ = 5). Experimental (symbols) and model fit (solid lines).

Fig. 3. Evolution of the reaction intermediates formed upon CWPO of EE2 (a) and DCF (b) with Fe₃O₄-R400 at 25 °C ([EE2]₀ = 1000 µg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = stoichiometric amount; [Fe₃O₄-R400] = 0.2 g L⁻¹; pH₀ = 5).

Fig. 4. Time-course of AZM, CLM and REM (individually treated) upon CWPO with Fe₃O₄-R400 at different temperatures ([Antibiotic]₀ = 1000 µg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = stoichiometric amount; [Fe₃O₄-R400] = 0.2 g L⁻¹; pH₀ = 5). Experimental (symbols) and model fit (solid lines).

Fig. 5. Evolution of the DCF during oxidation process with H₂O₂ in the presence of Fe₃O₄-R400 as catalyst at 17, 25, 50°C. ([DCF]₀ = 1000 µg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = stoichiometric amount; [Fe₃O₄-R400] = 0.2 g L⁻¹; pH₀ = 5). Experimental (symbols) and model fit (solid lines).

Fig. 6. Time-course of the pharmaceuticals upon CWPO of their mixture at 25 °C in different real WWTP effluents (a: WWTP1; b: WWTP2; c: WWTP3) ([Pharmaceutical]₀ = 1000 µg L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = 35 mg L⁻¹; [Fe₃O₄-R400] = 2.0 g L⁻¹; pH₀ = 5).

Fig. 7. Time-course of total coliforms, *E. coli* and DCF upon CWPO, H₂O₂ alone and Fe₃O₄-R400 alone at 25°C ([Fe₃O₄-R400] = 0.2 g L⁻¹; [H₂O₂]₀ = 10 mg L⁻¹) (experimental DCF data was obtained from Fig. 6).

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Table 1

Category	Compound	Structural formula	Reaction	H ₂ O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)*
Hormone	Estrone (E1) (270.4 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{18}H_{22}O_2 + 45H_2O_2 \rightarrow 18CO_2 + 56H_2O$	5.7
	17β-Estradiol (E2) (272.4 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{18}H_{24}O_2 + 46H_2O_2 \rightarrow 18CO_2 + 58H_2O$	5.7
	17α-Ethynylestradiol (EE2) (296.4 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{20}H_{24}O_2 + 50H_2O_2 \rightarrow 20CO_2 + 62H_2O$	5.7
Macrolide antibiotic	Azithromycin (AZM) (749.0 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{38}H_{72}N_2O_{12} + 105H_2O_2 \rightarrow 38CO_2 + 140H_2O + 2HNO_3$	4.8
	Clarithromycin (CLM) (748. g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{38}H_{69}NO_{13} + 100H_2O_2 \rightarrow 38CO_2 + 134H_2O + HNO_3$	4.6
	Erythromycin (ERM) (733.9 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{37}H_{67}NO_{13} + 97H_2O_2 \rightarrow 37CO_2 + 130H_2O + HNO_3$	4.5
Anti-inflammatory	Diclofenac (DCF) (296.2 g mol ⁻¹)		$C_{14}H_{11}Cl_2NO_2 + 33H_2O_2 \rightarrow 14CO_2 + 37H_2O + HNO_3 + 2HCl$	3.8

*Theoretical stoichiometric amount of H₂O₂ referred to an initial target pollutant concentration of 1000 μg L⁻¹.

Table 2

Category	Pharmaceutical	$k \cdot 10^2 (\text{min}^{-1}) (r^2)$			$E_a (\text{kJ mol}^{-1}) (r^2)$
		17°C	25°C	50°C	
Hormone	E1	5.0 (0.97)	12 (0.98)	48 (0.99)	51 (0.96)
	E2	3.0 (0.99)	6.1 (0.99)	22 (0.99)	46 (0.99)
	EE2	6.1 (0.97)	13 (0.98)	55 (0.99)	51 (0.96)
Macrolide antibiotic	AZM	3.0 (0.99)	6.2 (0.99)	28 (0.98)	52 (0.98)
	CLM	4.2 (0.99)	8.5 (0.96)	34 (0.99)	48 (0.99)
	ERM	5.3 (0.98)	9.5 (0.97)	37 (0.98)	45 (0.99)
Anti-inflammatory	DCF	0.9 (0.94)	3.1 (0.95)	26 (0.99)	77 (0.99)

Table 3

Parameter	WWTP1	WWTP2	WWTP3
pH	7.1	7.2	8.1
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	2.6	3.7	17.8
IC (mg L ⁻¹)	19.7	23.4	44.5
Conductivity (μS cm ⁻¹)	462	549	857
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	75.0	65.2	151.0
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	39.5	50.1	24.6
Fe ^{2/3+} (mg L ⁻¹)	0.1	0.1	1.6
Total coliforms (MPN/100 mL)	4786	1379	48700
<i>E. coli</i> (MPN/100 mL)	691	98	30500

Table 4

Category	Pharmaceutical	$k \cdot 10^2 \text{ (min}^{-1}\text{)} (r^2)$		
		WWTP1	WWTP2	WWTP3
Hormone	E1	13.3 (0.99)	6.3 (0.96)	8.3 (0.98)
	E2	8.5 (0.97)	5.2 (0.97)	3.1 (0.97)
	EE2	13.6 (0.99)	5.9 (0.96)	5.3 (0.99)
Macrolide antibiotic	AZM	7.6 (0.98)	5.7 (0.99)	5.5 (0.96)
	CLM	7.3 (0.98)	5.8 (0.99)	5.5 (0.97)
	ERM	10 (0.96)	6.2 (0.97)	5.7 (0.95)
Anti-inflammatory	DCF	6.9 (0.99)	4.3 (0.99)	6.5 (0.99)

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Supplementary Material revised

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